

IN CHILDREN 'S PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT

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Spirituality high , modern science possessed by the rich spiritual of our ancestors to his heritage owner came out generation never how external power , idea _ or ideology not at all own to the effect put down ca n't Such generation adult delivered of the people prospect bright future _ is great . So be independent initial years national education and education system reform to do our country of politics priority from directions to one became _

Our country leader Shavkat Mirziyoyev _ Uzbekistan Republic President to the position get in solemn to the ceremony dedicated Chambers of the Oliy Majlis joint meeting in his speech : " Our youth independent thinking , high intellectual and spiritual to potential have is the world scale own to peers never which in the field empty not coming people being maturity happy to find to be for our country and of our society there is strength and opportunities mobile " We will deliver , " he said separately emphasizing passed .

Indeed , today globalization during , information technologies century every youth in terms of mature by doing bring up very current and not at all late which cannot be is a task . The root strong a tree strong the wind and to hurricanes , snow and to storms endure give received like education _ from a young age perfect the possessed child is also in himself external from the effects protection

immunity form takes _

From the first days of our independence, it has been recognized as one of the priority tasks of our society to make the growing young generation mature in all aspects, spiritually perfect human beings. In this regard, the role of pre-school education organizations in educating young people, who are the foundation of our future, as perfect human beings, is incomparable. The work of preschool educational organizations can be considered multifaceted. From this point of view, the puppet theater is also very important in educating children's sense of sophistication. Puppet theater is pedagogically important due to the ability to directly communicate with children, exchange ideas in their "language", have special means of expression, convince children, and express their feelings about events. have

Our national theater art has historically traveled a long way, and its ancient roots are connected to folk games and performances.

Puppet theater has been used by many nations and peoples of the world since ancient times since known. SHE IS society in his life important importance occupation served in the development of people's way of life and thinking.

It should be noted that raising a child is not only the task of parents or teachers. Maybe that 's all including the neighborhood _ _ _ responsible _ Our people for nothing : "To a child They did not say that seven neighborhoods are parents . That's it in consideration now _ _ this decision with 3-6 years old before school education organizations cover not received the children their their parents Methodical manuals with provide through school to education preparation organize will be done .

This of work done increase state of politics main priority from directions one as of our republic continuously education system more reform to do regarding development of the road organic and step by step provides . Young generation perfect be _ in growing up , first of all , parents for example , before school education organizations employees initiative if , the same is temporary .

It is appropriate to remember the opinion of the great enlightener Mahmudhoja

Behbudi that "Theatre is a classroom".

Each _ baby doll theater to himself special and suitable national to the character have be _ the world civilization in history perfect a person bring up tool as service did _ Each puppet theater has the following effects on the child's psyche :

1. If the fairy tale chosen for the puppet theater matches the child's age and level of knowledge, the child will see it with his whole body and be interested in it;

2. It is known from our observations that some children show emotional states such as emotional excitement or fear, hatred, tears or laughter in relation to the hero of the fairy tale;

3. In the conversation at the end of the puppet show, the children express interest and joy about what they saw in the puppet show and want to see the puppet show all the time.

Theater not only gives joy and happiness to children, but also has a great educational value.

is also theatrical activity of children internal experiences , relationships , emotional of activity development ie work to the heroes relationship let them know to the situation try to enter such as circumstances with together in the child creative activity game , fantasy , knitting release through expand .

, in his speech at the opening of the first season of the Uzbek National Theater in Tashkent in 1914 , said, "...some of our people look at the theater, perhaps with the eyes of playfulness or clowning . original meaning " school " or " great ones" . school _ _ is a word . Theater all over the scene closed window done one home it seems that everyone to him if he enters , his good and evilness , guilt and defect seeing lesson it will happen was ". In our opinion , theater about this instructive words present even in the day importance did not lose .

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